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Synergies and Tensions between the EU Nature Restoration Regulation and the Water Framework Directive

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Europe's freshwaters remain under severe pressure, with most water bodies failing to achieve good ecological status despite two decades of effort under the Water Framework Directive (WFD). The newly adopted Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR) offers an unprecedented legislative push to reverse ecosystem degradation, including binding targets for river connectivity, floodplain reconnection and wetland recovery. As both instruments converge on similar pressures and shared landscapes, their alignment will be decisive for Europe's water resilience in the face of climate change. This Policy Brief explores how joint implementation of the WFD and NRR can transform restoration outcomes across Europe.

Key messages

- ➔ Align WFD and NRR planning cycles to maximise restoration impact. National Restoration Plans should be closely coordinated with River Basin Management Plans to ensure that NRR measures directly support WFD status improvements and vice versa, avoiding parallel, disconnected planning streams.
- ➔ Develop shared guidance and methodologies to connect NRR targets on how much should be restored with WFD ecological quality outcomes (the status of surface and ground waters).
- ➔ Recognise and harness synergies between the NRR Article 9 targets (free-flowing river, barrier removal, reconnecting floodplains) and WFD hydromorphology status. The NRR's focus on reconnecting river processes can raise restoration ambition, complement WFD assessments, and stimulate barrier removal to deliver improvements in WFD ecological status where traditional WFD measures alone have proven insufficient.

- ➔ **Ensure spatial coherence across ecosystem types.** While the WFD operates at river basin scale and the NRR at ecosystem scale, coordination is essential so that measures in agricultural, urban and forest ecosystems under the NRR support WFD freshwater objectives and vice versa without introducing local conflicts.
- ➔ **Integrate agricultural policy to avoid persistent pressures.** Misalignment with the CAP risks undermining restoration efforts, particularly in peatlands, floodplains and freshwaters within or downstream of intensively farmed catchments where land-use decisions strongly affect water bodies.
- ➔ **Strengthen funding coherence and administrative capacity.** Restoration ambitions under the NRR will only enhance WFD outcomes if funding streams, technical expertise and monitoring systems are harmonised rather than developed separately.
- ➔ **Promote restoration as a multi-benefit strategy.** Framing NRR-WFD synergies around climate resilience, biodiversity recovery, water quality, and flood risk reduction can build broader societal and political support.

Introduction

Europe's waters flow through landscapes burdened by decades of alteration: straightened channels, dams and weirs, drained peatlands, disconnected floodplains, and intensively managed agricultural areas. The health of rivers, lakes and groundwater is inseparable from the condition of their catchments. It is in this context that two major European policy instruments converge: the longstanding Water Framework Directive (WFD) and, more recently, the Nature Restoration Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2024/1991; NRR) that enshrines Europe's first continent-wide legally binding and directly applicable nature restoration requirements.

Under the WFD, Member States are obligated to secure good ecological status or potential for all surface and groundwater bodies, with deadlines stretching to 2027 and beyond. The WFD has been the driver of river and lake restoration over the past two decades. A multitude of restoration projects have been put into practice, but the overarching goal of achieving good status for all water bodies in Europe is far from being achieved. With the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR), a new player has entered the field with partly overlapping ambitions. The NRR, which entered into force 18 August 2024, commits the Union to ensuring "the long-term and sustained recovery of biodiverse and resilient ecosystems..." and sets out obligations for Member States to adopt national restoration plans, restore significant proportions of land (including inland waters) and sea, and address degraded ecosystems across terrestrial, freshwater, coastal and marine domains.

A prominent freshwater-related goal under the NRR (and the broader EU Biodiversity Strategy) is the restoration of at least 25 000 km of rivers by 2030 to a "free-flowing" condition, achieved through the removal (or adaptation) of primarily obsolete barriers and the reconnection of floodplains and wetlands (NRR Article 9.1).

Because many of the same pressures — barrier fragmentation, hydromorphological change, land-use intensification — degrade water bodies under WFD and impact biodiversity, there is great potential for synergies between the WFD and NRR. Equally, important risks of misalignment and unintended conflict may exist, requiring careful implementation to ensure policy cohesion.

This brief narrates the relationship between the two instruments, highlights where they reinforce each other, explores where tensions may arise, and concludes with recommendations to ensure the two frameworks become mutually reinforcing rather than operating in parallel or at odds.

How the Instruments Link: Reinforcing the Same Landscape

The WFD and NRR share a common story: the quality of freshwater and coastal waterbodies depends on the wider landscape, and restoration of nature broadly is part of achieving healthy water bodies. While under the WFD, a large number of river and lake restoration projects were implemented and successful, the overall share of water bodies in good ecological status has not increased. Most success has been seen in improving waterbodies from bad or poor to

moderate status, or for individual parameters. Restoration of freshwater ecosystems is mainly delegated to water management that is instrumental in improving in-stream structures and enforcing wastewater purification. But water management cannot change catchment land use, and can thus not directly influence stressors resulting from catchment agricultural activities and urbanisation. For example, the establishment of woody riparian vegetation has been identified as a key measure to improve ecological status particularly of smaller streams, but it has rarely been put into practice, as water management usually has little control on riparian land use.

With this in mind, the NRR may strengthen the WFD in several ways.

Firstly, the NRR introduces binding restoration targets for degraded ecosystems and Member States must identify ecosystems in need of restoration, establish national restoration plans, and implement area-based measures. In freshwater contexts this means that long-standing hydromorphological pressures (river fragmentation, disconnected floodplains, drained wetlands) that pose difficulties under WFD implementation may now gain a more structured restoration impetus.

Secondly, by explicitly addressing connectivity (in its many dimensions) and setting the 25 000 km free-flowing rivers objective, the NRR acknowledges that river health is about restoring flows, sediments, floodplains, and catchment processes. The European Commission's document on the criteria for free-flowing stretches (van de Bund et al. 2024) emphasises longitudinal, lateral and vertical connectivity including groundwater abstraction, which aligns well with WFD hydromorphology quality elements, which are essential for achieving good ecological status.

Thirdly, the NRR's requirement for cross-ecosystem restoration (terrestrial, wetland, coastal, urban), taking a more landscape approach, gives added impetus to measures in riparian areas and the wider catchment as a continuum. This means that many of the land-based pressures on waters bodies can now explicitly be addressed under the NRR. The WFD has always recognised that pressures originate outside of the water body, but implementation has often been constrained by sectoral divides. The NRR helps bridge that by offering a more integrated restoration lens (Blackstock et al. 2025).

Fourthly, the NRR article 11 (2) c demands for an increasing trend at national level of agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features. Strategically planned, this target could also benefit the WFD, if for example riparian buffer strips will be prioritised.

In short: the NRR can give the WFD a "catchment-scale boost" by making restoration of nature a core regulatory obligation, rather than something peripheral to water policy.

Where Tensions and Risks Could Emerge

Yet, even in this promising convergence, several critical tensions appear.

Timing and metrics misalignment: The WFD has established deadlines (2027, with some extensions) for achieving good status, and uses habitat or community quality, such as ecological status, as well as individual biological, chemical and hydromorphological parameters to measure success. The NRR operates on a different timescale (2030, 2040, 2050) and often uses restoration metrics of quantity, such as area restored or km of barrier removed. Linking quantitative NRR measures with qualitative ecological outcomes under the WFD will be challenging. Crucially, the gap is bidirectional: the NRR community is not required to translate restoration quantities into expected improvements in water-body status, while the WFD community often cannot specify how much and what type of restoration is required in a given basin to reach good status. This mutual ambiguity means that both policy communities have a shared responsibility to develop guidance and methodologies that connect restoration efforts with status objectives.

Spatial planning and institutional alignment: The WFD is organised around river basin districts and requires measures to achieve good status across all water bodies. Yet the NRR allows ecosystem-specific restoration planning (peatlands, forests, agricultural land, urban nature) and national restoration plans may adopt different spatial units. This could lead to restoration efforts that are less well aligned with basin management needs or water body obligations under the WFD. Added to this, the 25 000 km free-flowing rivers target is EU-wide and not broken down in the NRR into national quotas, leaving open the question of how Member States prioritise action within their basins. Given the very strict definition of free-flowing rivers, which have to be high status, they will most likely be restricted to remote and less populated areas in Europe.

Definition and measurement of “free-flowing”: The EC’s guidance emphasises that the concept of free-flowing rivers is not yet uniformly defined in EU law, and that operational criteria are being developed. The water community under the WFD may question how the free-flowing metric overlaps with hydromorphological quality elements. There is a risk of two parallel metrics that do not fully coalesce. At the same time, the free-flowing concept will help to shift attention toward full reconnection of river processes. While the metric differs from hydromorphological quality elements under the WFD, the two can be complementary: removing barriers enhances connectivity, sediment continuity and habitat quality, i.e. factors that underpin ecological status. The NRR can also be viewed as the long-awaited restoration complement to Natura 2000, filling gaps where the WFD has struggled to trigger large-scale hydromorphological improvement. However, these synergies need to be acknowledged to ensure that the emerging free-flowing metric becomes a driver rather than a parallel track.

Land-use and sectoral conflict (especially agriculture): Many restoration actions (e.g., peatland rewetting, river-floodplain reconnection) impinge on agricultural land, drainage infrastructure, or forestry systems¹. The NRR allows Member States an “emergency brake” with regards to the restoration of agricultural ecosystems under specific conditions. This creates potential for weaker implementation of restoration measures affecting water bodies. Unless agricultural policy (especially the Common Agricultural Policy) is fully aligned (Blackstock et al. 2025, Meier et al. 2025), the same pressures that cause WFD failures may persist even as restoration plans are drafted.

Implementation capacity and funding divergence: Water authorities implementing the WFD often cite limited budgets, staffing and long lag-times for ecological response. The NRR places additional demands on Member States and especially on local/regional bodies (engagement of stakeholders, drafting national plans, monitoring results). If restoration efforts become another “parallel stream”, there is risk of duplication, administrative overload, or mismatch in financing.

A Coherent Path Forward: What This Means for Policy and Practice

To ensure that the NRR strengthens, rather than complicates, WFD implementation, a number of actions are critical.

First, integrated planning must become the default. National restoration plans should be developed in concert with river basin management plans (RBMPs). Restoration measures for waters (e.g., barrier removal, floodplain reconnection and measures listed in NRR Annex VII. e.g. points 1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9) should be placed within the basin-scale context of the WFD, not treated as stand-alone ecosystem fixes. Freshwater-related habitats depend on the wider hydrological regime, and coordination with RBMPs can ensure that local terrestrial and wetland measures support, rather than inadvertently constrain, water-body objectives. Articulating these cross-scale synergies will help link NRR habitat restoration with WFD pressures and status improvements while respecting the ecological scales relevant for different habitat types.

Second, prioritisation of measures should favour those that deliver dual benefits, restoring nature and improving water status for both policy contexts. For example, removing obsolete dams achieves biodiversity benefits, restores sediment and nutrient flow, and also lifts hydromorphological pressures defined under the WFD. By choosing restoration sites based on both biodiversity and water-status gains, Member States can optimise use of resources and deliver compelling wins.

Third, monitoring and indicators must be harmonised. Restoration metrics (length of river restored, area of floodplain reconnected) should feed into water-status indicators and vice versa. The scientific and policy communities should work to ensure that metrics developed for “free-flowing” rivers under the NRR align with hydromorphological quality elements under the WFD, so that restoring connectivity actually results in measurable improvements in ecological status.

Fourth, funding and capacity must be aligned, ideally even beyond WFD and NRR and including funds to mitigate floods, droughts and increase water resilience. Agricultural funding (CAP) and structural/cohesion funds should be fully leveraged. By cooperation between water, nature,

¹ On cross-sectoral conflicts and support please compare

https://project-merlin.eu/files/merlin/downloads/deliverables/MERLIN_D4.7_Routemap_and_Annex_Nov2025.pdf

agricultural and other authorities, spatial planning, costs and administrative burdens can be reduced.

Framing restoration actions as win-win for multiple existing environmental and climate targets, such as water quality, flood risk reduction, biodiversity and climate resilience, will help build broad support across sectors (farmers, municipalities, utilities, NGOs). The convergence of the WFD and the NRR represents a unique policy moment for Europe's freshwater systems. It offers a second chance of giving way to a watershed-scale perspective that the WFD implementation has not fully achieved.

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